

THE CONSTITUENTS OF ALKANET ROOT (*ANCHUSA TINCTORIA*, LAM) PART II. ANCHUSIN AND ITS DERIVATIVES.

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A new colouring matter, anchusin ($C_{30}H_{36}O_9$), has been isolated from alkanet root. Anchusin is probably an anthraquinone derivative containing three hydroxyl groups, two of which are phenolic. β -Methylanthracene has been isolated by the distillation of anchusin with zinc dust under reduced pressure. The oxidation and bromination of anchusin have also been studied.

While the controversies regarding the constitution of alkannin, one of the colouring matters of alkanet, were going on (Betrabet and Chakravarty, *J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1933, 16A, 41) we thought it desirable to search for other colouring matters in the alkanet root as it is usually found that a naturally occurring compound is invariably associated with other compounds of the same type.

Gawalewski (*Chem. Zentr.* 1902, II, 1001) found that the alkanet roots contain also two colouring matters, anchusic acid ($C_{30}H_{30}O_7$) and alkanic acid ($C_{30}H_{28}O_8$) and Erikson (*Ber. Deut. Pharm. Ges.*, 1910, 20, 202) observed that of the two pigments one gives blue and another green solution with alkalis.

Anchusin has been obtained from the residue of the powdered alkanet root after extraction with petroleum ether. It is purified by precipitating the chloroform solution with benzene in which alkannin is very soluble whereas anchusin is very sparingly soluble. The precipitated anchusin is finally crystallised from alcohol in dark red micro-crystalline powder. The analytical results of anchusin and the analyses of the potassium derivative and the barium compound show that the molecular formula of anchusin is $(C_{10}H_{12}O_3)_3$. On acetylation a triacetylanchusin and tetra-acetylanchusin are obtained. Benzoylation gives a tribenzoyl derivative. The results indicate the presence of three hydroxyl groups in anchusin molecule and also an easily reducible carbonyl group. Methylation of anchusin gives a dimethoxy derivative which on further acetylation gives a dimethoxy-acetyl derivative showing thereby that two of the three hydroxyl groups are phenolic in character.

When distilled with zinc dust under high vacuum anchusin yields a small quantity of methylanthracene together with a yellow oil of peculiar smell. Anchusin thus appears to be an anthracene derivative.

On oxidation with 2*N*-nitric acid anchusin yields four different nitrogen-containing carboxylic acids of high melting points and oxalic acid. The yields of the acids are not sufficient for their identification.

It thus appears that alkannin and anchusin possess molecular complexity of the same order and the latter may be more saturated than the former. Moreover, it has been observed that on oxidation of alkannin with 2 *N*-nitric acid under similar condition it also gives a mixture of nitrogen-containing carboxylic acids of similar complexity. In spite of their non-identification it may be presumed that there is a good deal of similarity between these two colouring matters and both are derivatives of anthraquinone.

From the residue left after the extraction of anchusin, a third colouring matter has been isolated with chloroform which is insoluble in ether and benzene but soluble in chloroform. It gives indigo-blue solution with caustic soda and potash. We propose to designate it as 'Tincturin' instead of alkananin, (*Proc. Ind. Sci. Congress*, 1933, p. 206). Further work is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Isolation of Anchusin.—The powdered root bark (20 lbs) was extracted first with petroleum ether (50-60°) to remove alkannin and wax in a modified Soxhlet apparatus (Sando, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1924, **16**, 1125) till the final extract was colourless. The residues, left after extraction, were freed from the solvent and the dry powder was again extracted with ether in the same apparatus. The ethereal extract was freed from the solvent and a dark red amorphous and brittle product was obtained (8% of the root bark). It was digested with boiling benzene and the insoluble residue was dissolved in chloroform and precipitated with benzene. The process was repeated twice. Anchusin, thus obtained, was further purified by crystallisation from alcohol when it was obtained as a dark red micro-crystalline powder, decomposing above 300° with evolution of brown fumes after shrinkage at 185°. It is soluble in alcohol, acetone, acetic acid, pyridine, chloroform and sparingly soluble in benzene and ether and insoluble in petroleum ether. It can be precipitated from its green alkaline solution with acid. (Found : C, 66·8; H, 6·7. $C_{30}H_{38}O_6$ requires C, 66·67; H, 6·67 per cent).

The *barium salt* was prepared from alcoholic solution of anchusin (5 g.) with an ammoniacal solution of barium chloride. The greenish precipitate was filtered and washed thoroughly with water, alcohol and ether. [Found : Ba, 12·7. $(C_{30}H_{38}O_6)_2 Ba$ requires Ba, 11·3 per cent].

The *potassium salt* was obtained by treating an alcoholic solution of anchusin (5 g.) with an excess of alcoholic potash and the green precipitate was washed with alcohol and ether. (Found: K, 12.16. $C_{30}H_{34}O_9K$ requires K, 12.68 per cent).

Barium Potassium Compound.—An aqueous solution of the potassium salt of anchusin (5 g.) was mixed with barium chloride solution. The precipitate was washed with hot water till free from potassium chloride. [Found: Ba, 10.98. $(C_{30}H_{34}O_9K)_2Ba$ requires Ba, 10.64 per cent].

Triacetylanchusin.—Anchusin (50 g.), fused sodium acetate (100 g.) and an excess of acetic anhydride were heated under reflux for 5 hours at 130-40°. The crude acetyl derivative was washed with dilute alkali and then with water and the dry compound was again washed with boiling absolute alcohol several times to remove last traces of anchusin. The residue was dissolved in ethyl acetate and precipitated with absolute alcohol. It was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in microcrystalline powder, decomposing at 212-15° with shrinkage at 175-76°. [Found: C, 65.2; H, 6.05; $COCH_3$, 19.3; M.W. (Walker, Lumsden and Mc.Coy, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1900, 23, 353), 634.6. $C_{30}H_{33}O_9(COCH_3)_3$ requires C, 64.86; H, 6.3; $COCH_3$, 19.3 per cent. M.W. 666].

Tetraacetyl-leuco-anchusin.—A mixture of anchusin (15 g.), acetic anhydride (300 c.c.), zinc dust (45 g.) and fused sodium acetate (45 g.) was heated under reflux for 5 hours at 130-40°. After cooling the filtered deep yellow solution was poured into an excess of water and the yellow precipitate was collected and washed with dilute alkali and water. It was dissolved in ethyl acetate and precipitated with petroleum ether and washed with boiling absolute alcohol. The residue crystallised from glacial acetic acid in deep yellow crystalline powder, m.p. 210° (decomp.) shrinking at 190-91°. [Found: C, 65.4; H, 6.1; $COCH_3$, 24.77. $C_{30}H_{34}O_9(COCH_3)_4$ requires C, 64.3; H, 6.4; $COCH_3$, 24.3 per cent].

Dimethoxyanchusin was prepared from an alkaline solution of anchusin with dimethyl sulphate. The crude product was dissolved in chloroform and precipitated with petroleum ether and the precipitate digested with absolute alcohol and the residue crystallised from glacial acetic acid as microcrystalline powder, m.p. 240-42° (decomp.). It is a dark brownish powder, insoluble in benzene, petroleum ether and alcohol but soluble in acetone, chloroform, pyridine and ethyl acetate. [Found: C, 67.4; H, 6.9; OMe, 10.5. $C_{30}H_{34}O_7(OMe)_2$ requires C, 67.6; H, 7.0; OMe, 10.9 per cent].

Dimethoxyacetylanchusin.—Methoxyanchusin (5 g.) was acetylated as before and the product was extracted with benzene and precipitated with

petroleum ether. It was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in brown crystalline powder, not melting up to 330° . It is soluble in benzene, chloroform, ethyl acetate, pyridine, glacial acetic acid but insoluble in methyl and ethyl alcohol and petroleum ether. [Found: C, 67.3, H, 6.5; COCH_3 , 7.4; OMe, 9.8. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{33}\text{O}_7$ (OMe) $_2$ COCH_3 requires C, 66.9; H, 6.9; COCH_3 , 7.0; OMe 10.10 per cent].

Tribenzoylanchusin was prepared from anchusin (5 g.) in pyridine solution with benzoyl chloride. The crude product was dissolved in acetone, dehydrated with sodium sulphate and the residue, after the removal of the solvent, was dissolved in benzene and precipitated with petroleum ether. It was finally digested with absolute alcohol and the residue precipitated from benzene with petrol as brown powder, m.p. $226\text{--}28^{\circ}$ (decomp.). [Found: C, 72.0; H, 5.5. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{33}\text{O}_9$ (COC_6H_5) $_3$ requires C, 71.8; H, 5.63 per cent].

Bromination of Anchusin.—(i) Finely powdered anchusin (3 g.) was placed on a watch-glass and kept in a desiccator with an excess of dry bromine. The solid was occasionally stirred. A sticky mass was obtained after 5 days and was freed from excess of bromine by evacuation. The dark brown powder, thus obtained, was crystallised from absolute alcohol in brick-red powder, decomposing with shrinkage at $248\text{--}50^{\circ}$. (Found: Br, 37.9. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_6\text{Br}_4$ requires Br, 37.3 per cent). The residue from absolute alcohol was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in dark red microcrystalline powder, decomposing above 310° . (Found: Br, 47.4. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_6\text{Br}_6$ requires Br, 47.3 per cent).

(ii) Anchusin (5 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (70 c.c.) and acetic acid solution of bromine (30 c.c.) was added gradually at 0° with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was slowly brought to the room temperature and heated on a water-bath for $2\frac{1}{2}$ hours. The mixture after cooling was poured into an excess of cold water and the brick-red precipitate was collected, washed with water and dried over sulphuric acid under vacuum. It was crystallised from absolute alcohol in brick red powder, m.p. $160\text{--}65^{\circ}$ (decomp.). (Found: C, 34.9; H, 3.09; Br, 47.4. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_6\text{Br}_6$ requires C, 35.5; H, 2.96; Br, 47.3 per cent).

The residue from above was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in brick-red crystalline powder, m.p. above 310° (decomp.). (Found: Br, 48.2. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_6\text{Br}_6$ requires Br, 47.3 per cent). The residue from glacial acetic acid was crystallised from acetone in dark brown microcrystalline powder, decomposing without melting above 260° .

(iii) The above experiment (ii) was repeated without heating at the end. The precipitate after drying was extracted with absolute alcohol when most of it went into solution leaving a very small dark amorphous mass which could not be analysed.

The alcoholic solution gave a brick-red crystalline powder, decomposing above 270° . (Found : C, 41.7 ; H, 3.4 ; Br, 38.1. $C_{30}H_{32}O_9Br_4$ requires C, 42.0; H, 3.7 ; Br, 37.4 per cent).

Oxidation of Anchusin.—Finely powdered anchusin (20 g.) was heated to boiling for 5 hours with an excess of 2 N-nitric acid, and kept overnight. The insoluble residue (A) was filtered off from the brown solution (B).

The solution was concentrated to a small volume on a water-bath and finally evaporated to dryness in a desiccator over caustic potash and calcium chloride. The brown hygroscopic substance was digested with ether and the residue consisted of a colourless crystalline product and a fine brown powder. They were separated mechanically by stirring with ether. The brown highly hygroscopic powder containing nitrogen could not be crystallised from any solvent. The colourless crystalline powder was recrystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. $99-100^{\circ}$. It was confirmed to be oxalic acid (*p*-toluidino-compound, m.p. $264-65^{\circ}$). The ethereal solution gave a further quantity of oxalic acid, m.p. $99-100^{\circ}$ and a nitrogen-containing resinous substance which could not be identified.

The insoluble residue (A), when digested with hot water, left behind a small quantity of a solid which was crystallised from alcohol in yellowish orange crystalline powder, not melting up to 320° . It contains nitrogen and dissolves in sodium bicarbonate solution with evolution of carbon dioxide. The hot aqueous extract was evaporated nearly to dryness first in *vacuo* then over sulphuric acid in a desiccator. The orange powder, thus obtained, was extracted successively with ether, benzene and absolute alcohol. All these extracts gave high melting orange solids which vary from one another in their intensity of colour. They all contain nitrogen and dissolve in sodium bicarbonate solution with evolution of carbon dioxide.

Distillation of Anchusin with Zinc dust.—A mixture of anchusin with twice its weight of purified zinc dust was distilled under reduced pressure and the small amount of yellowish viscous oil, thus obtained, was dissolved in benzene and washed successively with caustic soda and water. The solution after dehydration with sodium sulphate gave a crystalline residue, which was recrystallised from alcohol in colourless plates, m.p. $199-200^{\circ}$. (mixed m.p. with a genuine sample of β -methylantracene).